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Assessment Of Waste Management Practices In Residential Estate In Awka, Anamabra State

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ABSTRACT

Waste management practices in residential areas are the methods households and communities use to generate, store, collect, transport, treat, recycle, and dispose of solid waste in a way that protects public health, preserves the environment, and keeps the neighborhood clean. This study accessed waste management practices in residential estates in Awka, Anamabra State. The objectives of the study were: (i) to examine the current waste management practices adopted in residential estates in Awka; (ii) to identify the type of waste generated in the residential estates; (iii) to evaluate the method of waste handling and storage practices; (iv) to examine the method of waste collection services in residential estates; (v) to assess the level of residents' awareness and participation in sustainable waste management practices; (vi) to identify the challenges and constraints faced by residents and waste managers in handling solid waste. The study adopts a descriptive survey design. The population consists of residents of selected private and public residential estates in Awka, Anambra State, along with estate managers and waste management officials. Findings indicate that waste management in residential estates in Awka is inadequate, unsustainable, and poorly coordinated. While private contractors are filling the gaps left by public agencies, irregular services and high costs continue to undermine efficiency. Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made, strengthening waste collection systems, provision of infrastructure, enforcement of environmental laws, community awareness and participation, adoption of technology, policy and institutional support for effective waste governance.

Keywords: Waste management, residential estates, waste disposal, solid waste, private contractors.

INTRODUCTION.

Waste management has become a critical urban challenge across the globe, especially in developing countries where rapid population growth and urbanization exert pressure on existing infrastructure. According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 2021), effective waste management is essential for safeguarding environmental quality, promoting public health, and ensuring sustainable urban development. Waste management practices refer to the processes involved in the collection, handling, storage, transportation, treatment, and final disposal of waste generated by human activities. The effectiveness of these practices often determines the level of cleanliness, safety, and sustainability within residential environments. Residential estates, which form a substantial portion of Nigerian urban settlements, generate large volumes of solid waste daily from food residues, plastics, paper, and other

domestic refuse. The effectiveness of waste management practices in these residential estates therefore plays a vital role in determining the quality of the residential environment.

In Awka, the capital city of Anambra State, waste management is coordinated primarily by the Anambra State Waste Management Authority (ASWAMA). However, due to limited government capacity, many residential estates rely on private waste contractors or engage in self-help practices such as open dumping, burning of refuse, or indiscriminate disposal in drainage channels. Such practices have been linked to environmental degradation, flooding during heavy rains, and public health risks, including malaria, cholera, and typhoid fever (Ezea & Roberts, 2014).

The government (ASWAMA) set laws and guidelines about waste management, standards for collection, separation, disposal, and approving waste management policy framework. They are licensed to issue, renew, revoke license from private waste collectors operating in the state. They manage dumpsites, plan for master waste disposal sites, plan and build drainage, public waste receptacles, and possibly transfer stations. Finally, they allocate funds for waste operations, carry out research, gather data on waste quantities/types, educate public on acceptable methods of waste disposal, recycling, etc. While the private contractors, collect solid waste from households (house-to-house), communal bins, commercial premises, transport it to dumpsites or designated disposal facilities. This is often under contract or through a service fee paid by the households. In some cases they do sorting, recycling, or hand-over to recyclers. Because government agencies may have limitations in fleet size, private contractors fill gaps by reaching some neighborhoods, more responsive schedules etc.

Some estates adopt more structured waste management strategies, such as regular collection services, waste segregation and recycling and many others lack sustainable systems for handling solid waste. The success of waste management in residential areas depends not only on government intervention but also on attitudes and participation of residents (Nzeadibe 2009). Effective waste management practices in residential estates typically include the use of standardized bins, timely evacuation of waste by authorized collectors, community sanitation exercises, and awareness campaigns to encourage waste reduction, reuse and recycling. Conversely, poor practices such as indiscriminate dumping, delayed collection, and lack of segregation contribute to environmental and health challenges in urban communities.

Therefore, assessing waste management practices in residential estates in Awka is necessary to identify existing gaps, evaluate the role of both government and private sectors and recommend strategies for improvement. Such assessment will not only enhance environmental sanitation within estates but also contribute to the broader goals of sustainable urban development and public health protection in Anambra State and Nigeria at large.

Residential estates in Akwa are currently experiencing various forms of waste management problems which is creating unpleasant site because some of the housing estates do not get to dispose their wastes until weekends when the contractors come around for evacuation while in some residential estates there is delay in collection of waste.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the establishment of the Anambra State Waste Management Authority (ASWAMA) and the presence of private waste contractors in Awka, the problem of inefficient waste management in residential estates persists. Many households in Awka still dispose of their waste through indiscriminate dumping in open spaces, drainage channels, and nearby bushes, or by open burning, which releases harmful gases into the atmosphere. These practices result in blocked drainage systems, flooding during the rainy season, and outbreaks of diseases such as cholera, malaria, typhoid, e.t.c.

Furthermore, the rapid growth of Awka as a capital city has led to the expansion of residential estates without corresponding improvements in waste management infrastructure. Waste collection services are often irregular or inadequate, while recycling and composting initiatives remain underdeveloped. Equally, there is limited awareness among residents about sustainable waste management practices, with most households showing little commitment to waste segregation or reduction.

The cumulative effect of these challenges is a deteriorating urban environment characterized by unsanitary living conditions, foul odours, increased vector-borne diseases, and environmental degradation. If these issues are not addressed, the quality of life in residential estates in Awka will continue to decline, posing serious threats to public health and sustainable urban development.

Research Aim and Objectives of the Study.

The aim of the study is to assess waste management practices in residential estates in Awka, Anambra State, with a view to identifying existing gaps and recommending strategies for effective and sustainable waste management. The objectives of the study are to examine the current waste management practices adopted in residential estates in Awka. To identify the type of waste generated in the residential estates. To evaluate the method of waste handling and storage practices. To examine the method of waste collection services in residential estates. To assess the level of residents' awareness and participation in sustainable waste management practices. To identify the challenges and constraints faced by residents and waste managers in handling solid waste.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Waste management in Nigerian cities has attracted substantial scholarly attention because rapid urbanization has outpaced the development of appropriate municipal services. Studies emphasize that household and estate-level practices (generation, segregation, storage, collection, treatment and final disposal) determine environmental quality and public health outcomes in urban residential areas. Several authors argue that institutional weakness, infrastructure gaps, and limited residents' participation are central to persistent problems in Nigerian cities, including Awka.

Existing studies indicate persistent weakness in estate-level waste management in Awka, from generation and disposal behaviors to institutional coordination and service delivery.

However, the literature also shows potential intervention points (community participation, integration of informal recyclers, operational optimization) that can improve outcomes.

Waste management practices refer to the various methods employed in the collection, handling, storage, transportation, treatment, and disposal of solid waste generated within residential estates. In the Nigerian context, particularly in cities like Awka, these practices are crucial for maintaining environmental quality and public health. They include activities such as waste segregation at the household level, use of communal or individual waste bins, engagement of government agencies or private contractors for waste collection, and participation in environmental sanitation exercises.

Some of the factors that hinder effective solid waste management in Awka metropolis are insufficient funding, inadequate waste management facilities, absence/non-implementation of bye laws and standards, unresponsive attitude of government and publics towards scavengers (David, Chinomso & Samuel, 2023). Amasuomo and Baird (2016) reported that households, industrial houses, farms, commercial buildings, hospitals, eateries, markets, construction and mining sites among others are the sources of waste in developing countries. The sources and types of waste in any urban or metropolitan setting should be adequately identified and factored into policy formulation if the aim of waste management is to be achieved.

According to (Folorunso, 2016), solid waste disposal poses fire hazards apart from being eyesores and sources of unpleasant odours, very frequently waste is dumped in drainages or canals and along water courses with impunity.

It is not uncommon that the health of the urban dwellers may be in jeopardy due to poor sanitation. There is high incidence of epidemics of unavoidable diseases like cholera, typhoid, diarrhea, malaria, bronchitis, asthma which often results from failure or delay in disposing wastes. The leakages and runoffs from landfills and open dumps affect adversely the quality of ground and surface waters by polluting them with salts, nitrates, and biodegradable organics (Oduola and Onibokun, 2016)

David, Chinomso and Samuel (2023) researched on evaluation of the challenges of effective solid waste management in Awka, Anambra State. The study revealed that major challenges to effective and efficient

waste management are insufficient funding, unavailability/inadequate waste management facilities, poor sorting of waste, unsupportive attitude of government/public towards scavengers, absence/ poor implementation of policies, use of crude means of solid waste management, inadequate number of private waste contractors, government's monopolization in waste management among others. The study recommended adoption of modern waste management techniques, education and awareness/orientation of the masses, enactment and implementation of the relevant laws and policies, engagement of private waste management firms and adoption of well-trained personnel for waste management always of making waste management more effective.

Nnatu (2018) carried out research in health implications of ineffective solid waste disposal for urban residents in Awka, the findings revealed that several factors mitigate effective waste disposal in Awka, the salient ones are rapid population growth, poor solid waste disposal culture, shortage of waste disposal personnel, inadequate resources of waste clearing and disposal and high rate of illiteracy. It was recommended that there should be public enlightenment campaign as well as introduction of environmental education at all levels of educational system. This will help to alter the attitude and value system towards environmental management by making the people to be sanitation conscious.

Agwu, Nnadozie & Akpaka (2025) studied on the factors affecting effective waste management practices in Owerri West Local Government Area (L.G.A) of Imo State. The study revealed that the factors affecting the effective waste management practices in the study, have been identified to include poor funding of the Imo State Management (ISWAMA), inadequate provision of recovery and recycling materials, limited infrastructure and professionals to execute the practices effectively, poor legislation which is a requirement for technological innovation or automation programme and poor awareness or public enlightenment programmes.

Nwachi, Agbo & Idenyi (2023) carried a research on the challenges of sustainable waste management in Nigeria, the study revealed that majority of the people believe that waste management is the sole responsibility of the government hence, the negative attitude towards waste management in the country. It also submits that government agencies are either not doing their work or they are understaffed with just 13.2% effectiveness. It concluded that if waste management is seen as an opportunity, government and individuals can earn good revenue from waste management business apart from creating positive impact in the society.

Babatunde and Ojetunde (2021), researched on public sector management of municipal solid waste in an emerging metropolitan setting in Minna, the study concluded that some of the existing waste management practices must be further strengthened by the appropriate authorities. The study was indicative of the lack of enforcement of waste management standards by the appropriate authority, poor quality of services provided, and the carefree attitude of the public towards waste management as severe bottlenecks to waste management services in Minna. The study recommended that the challenges merit consideration from policy makers and the state waste management agency so as to evolve a sustainable waste management practice from Minna metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a descriptive survey design, which is appropriate for assessing the existing waste management practices in residential estates. The design enables the researcher to collect data from a sample management agencies (ASWAMA/private contractors) in order to describe, analyze, and interpret prevailing conditions.

The population consists of residents of selected private and public residential estates in Awka, Anambra State, along with estate managers and waste management officials.

Residential estates in Awka will be stratified into public housing estates (e.g., Federal Housing, Iyiagu) and private estates (e.g., Udoka, Ngozika, Real Estate Layouts, Rockland, Dubai). From each stratum, estates will be selected purposively, while within estates, households will be sampled randomly. Sample size can be determined using Yamane's formula (1967), depending on population size. For instance,

within a population of 1,000 households, a sample of about 278 respondents would be adequate at 95% confidence level.

$$N = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \quad n = \frac{1000}{1 + 1000(0.05)^2} = 278$$

Where:

- . n = sample size
- . N = population size
- . e = margin of error (0.05)

For example

Procedure: The questionnaire will be self-administered to residents by the researcher. Interviews will be conducted with waste managers and ASWAMA officials/private contractors.

Data collected will be presented using tables and frequency distributions for clarity. Descriptive analysis (percentages, means, and standard deviations) to summarize demographic data and responses on waste management practices. Chi-square test (X^2) to determine relationship between estate type (public vs. private) and waste management practices and Likert scale analysis to assess data obtained from interviews and observation notes.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research question one: *What are the types of waste generated in the residential estates?*

Table 1: Types of waste generated in residential estates.

Type of waste	Frequency	Percentage %
Food waste/organics	210	84.0
Plastics and nylons	200	80.0
Paper/cartons	145	58.0
Cans/metal scraps	90	36.0
Glass bottles	70	28.0

Interpretation: The most common type of waste are food waste (84%) and plastics (80%), which aligns with household consumption patterns in Nigerian urban areas.

Research question two: *What are the various methods of handling waste and storage practices?*

Table 2: Waste handling and storage practices.

Practice	Yes (%)	No (%)
Use of covered waste bins	62.0	38.0
Segregation of waste at source	18.0	82.0
Burning of waste	44.0	56.0
Open dumping in bushes/drains	36.0	64.0

Interpretation: Waste segregation at source is very poor (only 18%), while open burning (44%) and dumping (36%) remain widespread. This indicates unsustainable waste handling practices.

Research question three: *What are the methods of waste collection services in residential estates?*

Table 3: Waste collection services in residential estates.

Variable	Category	Frequency
Waste collected by	Private contractors	180
	Self-disposal/burning	70
Frequency of collection	Daily	20
	Weekly	130
	Irregular	100

Interpretation: Private contractors are the main service providers (60%). Collection is mainly weekly, but irregular in 40% of cases and this is a major source of environmental nuisance.

Research question four: *What is the level of residents' awareness and participation in sustainable waste management practices?*

Table 4: Residents' Awareness and Participation.

Statement (Likert scale)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)
Aware of dangers of indiscriminate dumping	90.0	6.0	4.0
Believe recycling is important	70.0	15.0	15.0
Actively practice waste segregation	20.0	10.0	70.0
Participate in community sanitation exercise	55.0	20.0	25.0

Interpretation: While awareness levels of dangers of indiscriminate dumping are high with 90%, actual participation in proper practices like segregation (20%) remains low.

Research question five: *What are the challenges and constraints faced by residents and waste managers in handling solid waste?*

Table 5: Challenges of waste management in residential estates.

Options	Percentage (%)
Irregular waste collection services	68
Lack of standard bins or dumpsters	52
High cost of private waste contractors	44
Poor enforcement of sanitation laws	40
Residents' lack of commitment to sustainable practice.	38

Interpretation: Irregular waste collection services is the major challenges of waste management in residential estate with 68% followed by lack of standard bins or dumpsters with 52%. This shows that the respondents agreed that irregular waste collection services as the main challenges of waste management in residential estates.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Waste generation in Awka estate is dominated by food waste plastics, consistent with patterns observed in other Nigerian urban areas (Ezea & Robers, 2014; Nzeadibe, 2009)

Waste handling practices remain unsustainable, with low levels of segregation and high reliance on burning and open dumping.

Private contractors play a dominant role in waste collection, but services are irregular and sometimes costly, leading to lapses in disposal.

Although residents demonstrate high awareness of environmental hazards, actual participation in sustainable practices such as recycling and segregation is minimal, poor infrastructure, and low community participation remain the major barrier of effective waste management in Awka.

CONCLUSION

The findings demonstrate that waste management in residential estates in Awka is inadequate, unsustainable, and poorly coordinated. While private contractors are filling the gaps left by public agencies, irregular services and high costs continue to undermine efficiency. Furthermore, despite high awareness among residents, actual participation in sustainable practices such as waste segregation, recycling, and composting is minimal. Institutional challenges such as poor infrastructure, weak enforcement of environmental laws, and limited government support exacerbate the situation.

If not addressed, these issues will continue to contribute to environmental degradation, flooding and public health risks in Awka. Effective waste management in residential estates requires not only institutional reforms but also behavioral change among residents and stronger collaboration between government, private sector, and communities.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made;

1. Strengthening waste collection systems: ASWAMA should increase its operational capacity and improve collaboration effectively with private contractors.
2. Provision of infrastructure: Government and estate developers should provide standard waste bins and strategically located dumpsters within estates to discourage open dumping and burning.
3. Enforcement of Environmental Laws: strict enforcement of sanitation regulations is needed to penalize indiscriminate dumping and burning of refuse, while also regarding estates that demonstrate good waste management practices.
4. Community Awareness and Participation: Regular sensitization campaigns should be conducted to encourage residents to adopt sustainable practices such as segregation, recycling and composting. Monthly environmental sanitation exercises should also be revitalized and made mandatory in residential estates.
5. Adoption of Technology: GIS-based waste collection route optimization should be adopted to reduce operational costs and improve service efficiency in Awka.
6. Policy and Institutional Support: Adequate funding, monitoring, and transparency should be ensured in ASWAMA's operations, while estate managers should be empowered to coordinate waste collection and enforce compliance within their jurisdiction.

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